

IMPACT OF TETFUND ON STAFF TRAINING AND DEVELOPMENT IN NNAMDI AZIKIWE UNIVERSITY, AWKA, ANAMBRA STATE, 2014 TO 2020

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Keywords: Staff training, Development, TETFund, Research, Output.	Abstract: <i>This study is an investigation of the impact of Tertiary Education Trust Fund on staff training and development in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020. The motivation for the study was as a result of the importance of staff training and development in the attainment of the goals of organizations and how the interventions of TETFund has fared in this regard. The specific objectives of the study were, among others, to ascertain the relationship between TETFund academic staff training and development programmes and quality of research output in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020. Based on the objectives of the study, three research questions and hypotheses were formulated and tested for the study. Relevant literature was thoroughly reviewed and the study was anchored on the human capital theory. Data for the study was collected from a sample size of 381, drawn from a population of 8,008 using the Taro Yamane formula. The data collected were presented using simple percentage and the hypotheses were tested using Pearson correlation statistical tool. The study found out that, the TETFund modalities for funding of staff training and development programmes in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020 are practicable. That there is a relationship between TETFund academic staff training and development programmes and quality of research output in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020. On the basis of the findings from the study, it was therefore, recommended that a committee should be set up to review research output of grant beneficiaries on the completion of their studies. Those that are novel and addresses</i>
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specific societal challenges should be adopted and channeled to the appropriate government agencies for action to be taken on them.

Introduction

There is a consensus among experts and practitioners in organizational behavior and human resource management that the human component is the most complex and most important component in all organizations (Bankole, 2003). There are basically four factors of production – land, labour, capital and entrepreneur. While the entrepreneur has absolute control over the use of land and utilization of capital, he has no such absolutism over the human component in the production process. Managing the human aspect of an organization's resources requires that just like machines, tools and equipment that needs to be serviced, repaired and maintained to ensure optimum performance; human resources have to be motivated, trained and developed to not only master the tasks, duties and responsibilities required of the employee from the organization, but to discharge those duties at the least possible cost to the organization.

Training and development are important aspects of the core functions of the human resource department of any organization. In general terms, the human resource management in organizations focuses on objectives of an organization which is achieved through cooperative efforts and actions of people utilizing available resources. The ultimate goal of the human resource department of an organization

is to work for the welfare of workers in the organization vis-à-vis attainment of the core mandate of the organization (Chirchir, 2013). Training could be on the job or off the job. It could take place within the organization or outside the organization (Chirchir, 2013). In Nigeria and all around the world, tertiary institutions are regarded as citadels of learning, fountains of scholarly development and a breeding ground for leaders at all levels in the society, be it political, business, technical or administrative. For most organizations, especially those in the formal sector, certificate qualifications from tertiary institutions – especially universities - are required from applicants before employment, especially at the higher levels of the organization.

This makes the university a very important institution for capacity building and human capital development. Globally, investment in university education particularly and tertiary education in general are critical components of national development efforts. Nations today depend increasingly on knowledge, ideas and skills which are produced through research conducted in the universities. By implication, university staff, who are often considered as custodians of knowledge and innovation needs to be abreast of current trends in their areas of discipline because it is impossible for one to give what he or she does not have. Training and

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capacity building for university staff is sacrosanct in view of the fact that they are the gatekeepers of knowledge and innovation.

The whole essence of staff training and development is to enhance the productivity and services delivered by the employees of an organization. According to Adeniyi (2011), workers' training and development is an important programme that promotes the workers' efficiency and effectiveness in an industrial set up. The sum total of employees' productivity, demonstrated through efficiency and effectiveness, translates to the overall productivity of the organization. For an organization like a university, the yardstick for measuring productivity is quite complex and the manifestations of efficiency and effectiveness are varied.

From the obvious ones that relate to its quality of research output, contribution to knowledge and problem solving in the society as well as how the institution responds to changes in its operational dynamics occasioned by advancement in technology, to the less noticeable ones that has to do with record keeping, student-staff relationship, prompt processing of students' results and mobilization for national youth service, quality of students graduated, among others. Performance indicators for tertiary institutions are not just varied and complex, they are also dynamic and changes with time, human and societal needs per time.

Thus, to keep the tertiary institutions abreast of recent trends and developments – as a premier

institution involved in capacity building and human capital development on a massive scale, constant training and development programmes are necessary. This informs the establishment of the Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) as an improvement from the defunct Education Trust Fund (ETF) with the responsibility to – among other things – provide intervention funds for tertiary institutions especially in the areas of staff training and development.

The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) published Guidelines for accessing TETFund intervention funds (2017) chapters 11 to 13, outlines the conditions to be met to assess grants for staff training and development. In view of the foregoing, this empirical study provides an assessment of the impact of TETFund on staff training and development in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020.

Statement of the Problem

The decay in the education sector, especially the tertiary education sector from the 1980s and beyond, necessitated the need for intervention to save the situation. The intervention is all the more necessary in view of the fact that many other sectors of the economy – especially the formal sector – depend on the instructional guidance from tertiary institutions to equip their human resources or prepare their potential employees to be qualified for formal employment.

It is often said that one cannot give what he or she does not have, an indication that the

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productivity of an employee per time is a function of their knowledge, skill, expertise and a stimulating work environment. One of the variants of staff training and development is further studies. There are funds and grants that staff members can assess to further their education especially at postgraduate levels. The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund), provides funding opportunity in this regard. However, it has been observed that accessibility of these funds is always a challenge.

In Nnamdi Azikiwe University where the research is situated, many of the PhD holders that the researcher interacted with claimed that they obtained their degrees under self-sponsorship. The extent to which funding for research, conferences and other academic development endeavours by the Tertiary Education Trust Fund is still a subject of debate that requires critical scholarly evaluation. According to Ileka and Igbokwe-Ibeto (2024) some challenges are inherent in the assessment of the fund by academic staff in Nigerian Universities especially in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. This ranges from but not limited to delay in the approval of fund, stringent conditions attached to fund assessment such as approval of insufficient fund for the expected programme administrative bottlenecks among others (Ileka & Igbokwe-Ibeto, 2024).

Confidential files accessed by the researcher indicates that only 79 beneficiaries have been sponsored for academic staff training and development programmes in the periods

between 2014 to 2020. This is out of more than triple the number that applied. Also for the period under review, the institution received from TETFund over a billion naira for the same purpose. With this, it may appear that the modalities for assessing these funds appears to constitute a stumbling block for university staff in general and academic staff in particular.

For instance, in chapter 12 of the Guidelines for accessing TETFund intervention funds (2017), section 1202 (f)(i), only a maximum of seven academic staff of a department could attend a group conference within a given intervention year. Also, the TETFUND sponsorship for further studies is skewed in favour of those in science and technology based courses (60 percent), while courses in the arts, management and social sciences are left with the remaining 40 percent. This precondition places a barrier on the majority of the academic staff in these other fields of endeavor which the agency has wrongly assumed are not too important to the development of the society. Another limitation is that TETFUND insists that all PhD programme under their sponsorship must not exceed three years without considering the fact that circumstances beyond the candidates control can impact negatively to elongate the duration of the study.

In assessing the impact of TETFund on staff training and development in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020, there is the need to look at the quality of the research output of beneficiaries of the

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intervention scheme that have completed their studies. The whole essence of sponsorship for further studies, especially doctorate and post doctorate research studies is to improve the body of knowledge. There is a condition that upon completion of their studies, beneficiaries will have to deposit a copy of their research output with TETFund. Sadly, this is hardly the case and even where they are submitted, the research findings are hardly evaluated to ascertain how it have addressed particular issues in the society locally or globally.

Also from the records, many staff who benefit from foreign TETFund sponsorship for further studies do not return to deploy their knowledge and skill to the benefit of the organization. This situation is not peculiar to Nnamdi Azikiwe University as it has forced TETFund to cancel foreign sponsorship in many departments and faculty. All of these creates a huge question mark as to the impact of TETFund on staff training and development, thus necessitating the need to conduct this empirical research to assess the impact of TETFund on staff training and development in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020.

Objectives of the Study

The broad objective of this study is an assessment of the impact of TETFund on staff training and development in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020. Specifically, the study addressed the following objectives:

1. To ascertain the practicability of TETFund modalities for funding staff training and development programmes in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020.
2. To examine the effect of TETFund academic staff training and development programmes on the quality of research output in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020.

Research Hypotheses

The following hypotheses have been formulated to guide the study:

- 1) **H₀**: TETFund modalities for funding of staff training and development programmes in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020 are not practicable.
- 2) **H₀**: TETFund academic staff training and development programmes has no positive effect on the quality of research output in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020.

Conceptual Review: Training and Development

Some authors use the terms “training” and “development” as synonyms. However, some view the two concepts as being different. Jones, George and Hill, (2000) believe that training primarily focuses on teaching organisational members how to perform their current jobs and helping them acquire the knowledge and skills they need to be effective performers. Development on the other focuses on building the knowledge and skills of organisational

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members, so that they will be prepared to take on new responsibilities and challenges. In the view of Adamolekun (1983), staff development involves the training, education and career development of staff members. The purpose of training and development has been identified to include: creating a pool of readily available and adequate replacements for personnel who may leave or move up in the organization; enhancing the company's ability to adopt and use advances in technology because of a sufficiently knowledgeable staff; building a more efficient, effective and highly motivated team, which enhances the company's competitive position and improves employee morale; and ensuring adequate human resources for expansion into new programs. In the views of White (2010), training is seen as a process of learning. It involves the application of acquired knowledge aiming at better performance of the employees, Training can also be defined as a process of assisting employees to acquire or develop knowledge, skills, techniques and attitudes and experiences which enable them to make most effective contributions to their combined efforts, to meet organizational objectives. Randall Schuler (2000) refers to training as the act of improving competencies needed today or in the future while development refers to improving competencies over the long term. Also management training is considered to be a process of enhancing an employee's capacity to handle greater responsibilities successfully (Singh and Vinnicombe, (2014). Cole (2010) note

that training includes all those activities, which enable, make easier and accelerate knowledge acquisition necessary for successful business activity. Training can confirm to people the value of what they are already doing, pass on new skills to colleagues in the workplace, raise general awareness and improve morale. In addition, training can also play an important role in improving workers' effectiveness. Whether training is part of an ongoing process of professional development or simply about learning a specific skill, it improves their skills and knowledge and helps them carry-out their jobs more effectively. Employees who are actively engaged in their jobs work with passion and feel a profound connection to their company. They help move the organization forward and they believe they can positively impact quality of their organization's products (White, 2010).

Types of Training Programmes

They are different types of training programmes. Some of these types, according to Tai, (2006) are discussed below:

On-The-Job Training: On-the-job training is carried out in the workplace during the working days. It involves grooming, coaching and mentoring an employee in the process of their normal daily official activities. On-the-job training, according to management professionals, is a cost effective way of getting employees acquainted to the nitty-gritty of their job duties and responsibilities without affecting organisational production time and man hour. On the other hand, however, it has been argued that

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on-the-job training will increase fatality rates as a result of trials and error.

Off-The-Job Training: Off-the-job training, like the name implies, takes place outside the precinct of the immediate work environment. Even when such exercises are conducted within office premises, it does not interfere or have any effect on the organisation's normal work activities. In other words, off-the-job training does not utilize real life work situations in their grooming, coaching or mentoring exercise. Off-the-job training can involve group discussions, one-to-one tutorials, lectures, reading, training courses, seminars and workshops. Off-the-job training is advisable when a large number of staff have a similar training requirement and when there are adequate skills and resources for the design and provision of training.

Management Development: Employers and supervisors are the ones who plan on work to be done and ensure that they supervise their subordinates to perform their daily tasks to lay down standards by the organization. In this case, they need to be equipped with required skills and knowledge to enable them to perform their duties smoothly. According to Milkovich and Boudreau (2009), unlike skills training, management development often focuses on less well-defined skills, and the manager often shoulders a greater responsibility for personal development. A specific type of training for this group therefore is management development training. Management development increases effectiveness of the organization as managers'

performance are improved due to being clearly informed of the responsibilities and by standardizing agreeable and measurable objectives.

The managers with further potentials are identified and equipped for more senior posts. Through this type of training, organizations are provided with adequate number of persons to succeed managerial positions. However, this type of management training/ development sometimes may be hazardous to organizations as non-managers are not exposed to this training. Thus should they be appointed or promoted to managerial positions it may take time for them to cope. This type of training is also very expensive and in many organizations this training has been made at the expense of other employees through a select few for training.

Professional Training and Legal Training: In some jobs, professional training must be done on an ongoing basis. Professional training is a type of training required to be up to date in one's own professional field. For example, tax laws change often, and as a result, an accountant for H&R Block must receive yearly professional training on new tax codes. Lawyers need professional training as laws change such training is normally provided through full time attendance of courses in higher learning institutions/ colleges or through part-time and distance learning. Some organizations have paid a high cost for not properly training their employees on the laws relating to their industry.

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Professional training is normally given externally and is usually required for specific professions in which updates occur often, as in the accounting industry. Brum (2007) while acknowledging that training has been used extensively by organizations as a competitive strategy, notes that there are significant varying debates among professionals and scholars as to the effect that training has on both employee and organizational goals. He posits that one school of thought argues that training leads to an increase in turnover while the other states that training is a tool that can lead to higher levels of employee retention but regardless of the school of thought, most professionals agree that employee training is a complex human resource practice that can significantly impact a company's success.

Refresher Training: At the time of initial appointment of employees, they are formally trained for their jobs. But with the passage of time, they may forget some of the methods which were taught to them and become outdated because of technological development and improved management and production. Hence, refresher training is arranged to existing employees in order to provide them an opportunity to revive and also to improve their knowledge. Sahinidis and Bouris (2008) notes that directly the role of training programs is seen as a measure of improving employee capabilities and organizational capabilities i.e. when the organization invests in improving the knowledge and skills of its employees, the investment is

returned in the form of more productive and effective employees.

Internship Training: Internship training programmes have become popular these days because of cooperation between employers and vocational institutes. Under this method, the vocational institute enters into an arrangement, with a business enterprise, to provide practical knowledge to its students. Internship training is usually meant for such vocations where advance theoretical knowledge is to be backed up by practical experience on the job. For instance, engineering students are sent to big industrial enterprises to gain practical work experience and medical students are sent to big hospitals to get practical knowledge.

Problem-Solving Training: It is important that employees are trained to make split-second decisions. Rough seas, power failures, fire or even running out of margarita mix can cause a serious situation at sea. Trainers and trainees need to work together and quickly solve any problem that occurs. Problem-solving training is training on how to analyse problems and make decisions and is mandatory for all crew trainees. Trainees will learn how to identify problems, analyse problems, assess solutions, implement solutions and monitor outcomes. There are many benefits to offering problem-solving training to employees. Employees will be more likely to: Offer creative solutions to problems and Collaborate on problem-solving.

Technical or Technology Training: Depending on the type of job, technical training will be

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required. Technical training is a type of training meant to teach the new employee the technological aspects of the job. In a retail environment, technical training might include teaching someone how to use the computer system to ring up customers. In a sales position, it might include showing someone how to use the Customer Relationship Management (CRM) system to find new prospects. In a consulting business, technical training might be used so the consultant knows how to use the system to input the number of hours that should be charged to a client. In a restaurant, the server needs to be trained on how to use the system to process orders. Let's assume your company has decided to switch to the newest version of Microsoft Office. This might require some technical training of the entire company to ensure everyone uses the technology effectively. Technical training is often performed in-house, but it can also be administered externally.

Understanding Knowledge, Skills and Attitudes

Learning objectives must be established and adhered to when developing a training program – otherwise, training activities may bear few results. Townsell (2013) insists that regardless of the training subject matter, training objectives should always address each component of the acronym KSA, which stands for *knowledge, skills and attitudes*. Each KSA element is an important part of learning and development. Training (regardless of the subject) should result in improved knowledge, improved skills and an

improved attitude toward the subject matter and training process. Utilizing these elements as the framework of objective development will result in tangible, measurable outcomes.

Knowledge: Knowledge is a belief that is true and justified, usually based on verifiable facts. This definition has led to its measurement by methods that rely solely on the correctness of answers. A correct or incorrect answer is interpreted to mean simply that a person knows or does not know something. Such methods of measurement have serious deficiencies that can be alleviated by expanding the definition of knowledge to include the test-taker's certainty. The person's certainty about the answers on a test captures important, but now neglected, dimensions of knowledge. Historical roots of certainty as an essential component of knowledge, and some practical benefits of including it, are discussed. An epistemic method is described which allows people to indicate "How sure are you?" about the correctness of each of their answers.

Knowledge is sometimes viewed as if it was a concrete manifestation of abstract intelligence, but it is actually the result of an interaction between intelligence (capacity to learn) and situation (opportunity to learn), so is more socially-constructed than intelligence. Knowledge includes theory and concepts and tacit knowledge gained as a result of the experience of performing certain tasks. Understanding refers to more holistic knowledge of processes and contexts and may be distinguished as know-why, as opposed know-

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that. A distinction is often made between general knowledge, which is essential irrespective of any occupational context or so fundamental as to be considered basic life knowledge, and knowledge that is specific to a sector or particular group of occupations and only likely to be encountered in such context. This specialised knowledge is necessary for meeting content specific demands and solving content-specific tasks. In contrast to general intellectual abilities, one can consider arbitrary knowledge as a demand specific competence.

Skills: A skill is learning to carry out a task with pre-determined results often within a given amount of time, energy, or both. Skills can often be divided into domain general and domain-specific skills. For example, in the domain of work, some general skills would include time management, teamwork and leadership, self-motivation and others, whereas domain-specific skills would be useful only for a certain job. Skill usually requires certain environmental stimuli and situations to assess the level of skill being shown and used.

Usually the term skill is used to refer to a level of performance, in the sense of accuracy and speed in performing particular tasks (skilled performance). Skilled performance has long been a subject of psychological enquiry and is of

obvious interest to employers. Bryan and Harter (1897; 1899), who undertook one of the earliest systematic studies of (practical) skills acquired in the work environment (by telegraph operators at Western Union), demonstrated that skill acquisition involves a series of stages associated with reaching plateaux of performance and that improvements continue well beyond achieving an adequate level.

Careers & Employability Service (CES, 2016) note that employers look for a range of skills in job applicants, many of which are common to a number of different career areas. Those most frequently mentioned are communication, team working, leadership, initiative, problem-solving, flexibility and enthusiasm. Indeed, many skills overlap with one another. Leadership, for example, encompasses a number of other skills including cooperating with others, planning & organising, making decisions and verbal communication. Verbal communication itself involves various means of communication, some of which you may find easier than others - talking over the phone, making a presentation to a group or explaining something to a person with a more limited understanding of the topic. By improving one skill, you may also improve in a number of others.

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Table 1: Preferred skills by employers

Verbal Communication	1	Able to express your ideas clearly and confidently in speech
Teamwork	2	Work confidently within a group
Commercial Awareness	3	Understand the commercial realities affecting the organisation.
Analysing & Investigating	4	Gather information systematically to establish facts & principles. Problem solving.
Initiative/Self-Motivation	5	Able to act on initiative, identify opportunities & proactive in putting forward ideas & solutions
Drive	6	Determination to get things done. Make things happen & constantly looking for better ways of doing things.
Written Communication	7	Able to express yourself clearly in writing
Planning & Organising	8	Able to plan activities & carry them through effectively
Flexibility	9	Adapt successfully to changing situations & environments
Time Management	10	Manage time effectively, prioritising tasks and able to work to deadlines.

Source: Careers & Employability Service (CES, 2016)

Job Attitude: The third desired outcome of learning encompasses one's beliefs and/or opinions, which are manifested in behavior. These factors will determine a person's motivation to learn and will subsequently affect one's ability to gain both knowledge and skills. *Attitudes* are affected by feelings towards the

subject matter and the overall learning process. Most people who have led a training class or seminar experienced the effects of a participant's negative attitude toward the training. This is often the result of a bad experience related to a prior training or the subject matter. It should be the goal of every training program to improve

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attitudes and behaviors toward both the training process and the subject matter. This must be considered and addressed in the development phase. Failure to do this will result in low retention levels and a failed training program.

The old saying, “fail to plan, plan to fail,” holds very true when establishing objectives, as programs that lack tangible and planned learning objectives often fail. Ensure learning objectives are your primary focus as you plan and develop a safety training program. Without a solid foundation of learning objectives, your training program has no more than a chance at success; with learning objectives, you’re on your way to successful program development (Townsell 2013). Each person has a different level of attitude about their job and that attitude can be rated, if you will, by how involved the individual is in his or her job. In this lesson, we will look at job attitudes as they relate to job satisfaction, commitment, engagement, and more.

TETFUND and Staff Training and Development in Nigeria Tertiary Institutions (Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka)

The Tertiary Education Trust Fund (TETFund) was originally established as Education Trust Fund (ETF) by the Act No 7 of 1993 as amended by Act No 40 of 1998 (now repealed and replaced with Tertiary Education Trust Fund Act 2011). It is an intervention agency set up to provide supplementary support to all level of public tertiary institutions with the main objective of

using funding alongside project management for the rehabilitation, restoration and consolidation of Tertiary Education in Nigeria.

There are several departments at TETFUND some of which are the departments of Academic Staff Training and Development (AST&D), Strategic Planning and Development, Human Resources and General Administration, Finance and Investment, Education Support Services, Information and Communication Technology (ICT), Physical Infrastructure, Monitoring and Evaluation, among others.

The main source of income available to the Fund is the two percent education tax paid from the assessable profit of companies registered in Nigeria. The Federal Inland Revenue Services (FIRS) assesses collects the tax on behalf of the Fund. The funds are disbursed for the general improvement of education in federal and state tertiary educations specifically for the provision or maintenance of:

- Essential physical infrastructure for teaching and learning
- Institutional material and equipment
- Research and publications
- Academic staff training and development and
- Any other need which, in the opinion of the Board of Trustees, is critical and essential for the improvement and maintenance of standards in the higher educational institutions (TETFUND official website <https://tetfundserver.com/index.php/tetfund/>)

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TETFUND: Department of Academic and Staff Training and Development

The Academic Staff Training and Development (AST&D) became a fully functional Department in the year 2013. The AST&D Department has three (3) main Academic/Content- based Interventions namely:

1. TETFund Scholarship for Academic Staff (TETFSAS) Programmes introduced in 2008;
2. Conference Attendance (CA)- Programmes introduced in 2010; and
3. Teaching Practice (TP)-introduced in 2012

The AST&D Department has the responsibility for effective co-ordination and implementation of the various intervention lines domiciled in the Department for the overall attainment of the mandate of the Fund. The basic functions of the AST&D) Department are:

1. Ensuring effective co-ordination as well as delivery of Academic-based intervention Programmes as designed by the Fund in accordance with its mandate;
2. Ensuring the vetting of submissions received from all TETFund Beneficiaries as stipulated in the Fund's guidelines;
3. Ensuring that allocated intervention funds are accessed by Beneficiary Institutions and facilitate processing of disbursements of all intervention programmes domiciled in the department in line with extant guidelines and procedures;
4. Ensuring prompt and quality delivery of all TETFund educational intervention programmes domiciled in the Department;

5. Ensuring cordial, effective and sustainable partnership with beneficiaries of TETFund Scholarship for Academic Staff (TETFSAS) intervention programmes;
6. Inspecting and verifying the deployment of funds disbursed under the local and foreign components of the TETFund Scholarship for Academic Staff Intervention Programmes, as well as Teaching Practice Supervision programme; and
7. Providing advice to Management on issues relating to Intervention Programmes domiciled in the Department.

Theoretical Framework

The study was anchored on the human capital theory. The term 'human capital theory' was introduced by Theodore W. Schultz in a 1961 article published in the American Economic Review, called investment in human capital. According to Wuttaphan, (2017), the human capital theory states that a different level of education and training contribute to a different level of wages and salaries. The more the knowledge, skill and ability, the more the likelihood to get a better job (Blair, 2012).

Generally speaking, the human capital theory is premised on the assumption that individuals, organizations and the society at large derive economic benefit from investing in people. The nature and character of the investment is usually in the areas of health, social services and education. There are instances where organizations provide medical and health insurance for its staff, staff clinic, staff canteen,

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staff bus, etc. However, scholars have placed more emphasis on education and its sub variant, training because they have direct tangible implication on workers' performance and the general growth and development of the organization.

Proponents of the human capital theory believe that formal education is highly instrumental and necessary to improve the productive capacity of a population. In short, human capital theorists argue that an educated population is a productive population. Human capital theory emphasizes how education increases the productivity and efficiency of workers by increasing the level of cognitive stock of economically productive human capability, which is a product of innate abilities and investment in human beings. The provision of formal education is seen as an investment in human capital, which proponents of the theory have considered as equally or even more worthwhile than that of physical capital (Woodhall, cited in Almendarez, 2011).

Human capital theory has been considered as one of the economics theories of Human Resource Development (HRD), others being the Scare Resource Theory and Sustainability Theory. According to Swanson (1999), because performance improvement takes place in organizations that are economic entities, it (performance improvement) must therefore, call upon an economic theory at its core. In addition, management theories and methods should be properly viewed as useful derivatives of

economic theory. In order to survive in a competitive knowledge based economy as well as keeping sustainability, human capital as an economic theory needs to be considered seriously (Wuttaphan, 2017). Human capital theory can improve a firm's performance and explain the significance of labor maximization and how an organization can accumulate employees' knowledge, skill, and ability by investing in humans through training and educating to enhance an employee's capacity to work effectively.

The human capital theory stresses the significance of education and training as the key to participation in the new global economy. In one of its recent reports, the Organization for Economic Cooperation and Development (OECD), for example, claims that the radical changes introduced to the public and private sectors of the economy of most countries over recent years in response to globalization will be severe and disturbing to many established values and procedures. In another report it explains internationalism in higher education as a component of globalization. Thus the OECD asserts that internationalism is a means to improve the quality of education. In keeping with human capital theory, it has been argued that the overall economic performance of the OECD countries is increasingly more directly based upon their knowledge stock and their learning capabilities. Clearly, the OECD is attempting to produce a new role for education in terms of

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human capital subject required in globalized institutions.

Conclusively, the human capital theory believes that investment in human capital will lead to greater economic outputs. However, the validity of the theory is sometimes hard to prove and contradictory. In the past, economic strength was largely dependent on tangible physical assets such as land, factories and equipment. Labor was a necessary component, but increases in the value of the business came from investment in capital equipment. However, modern economists seem to concur that education and health care are the key to improving human capital and ultimately increasing the economic outputs of the nation (Becker 1993).

Methodology

The research design adopted for this study was the descriptive survey method. This study utilized a modified Likert 5-point response scale which are; 'Strongly Agree' (5 points), 'Agree' (4 points), 'Strongly Disagree' (3 points), 'Disagree' (2 points) and 'Undecided' (1 point). Both

primary and secondary sources of data were employed in this study. The population of the study constitute staff of Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka. The staff strength of the university as at 2021 stood at 8,008, comprising of 2,673 academic staff and 5,335 non-academic staff.

Taro Yamane (1967) method was used for sample size determination. A 95% confidence level was equally assumed. Thus, a sample size of 381 was used for the study. Both purposive and random sampling techniques were used to ensure that the sample size reflect the true representation of the population of the study and that the respondents cut across faculties and departments. Data generated from primary sources was analyzed using descriptive statistics such as tables and simple percentages. Consequently, in order to test the hypotheses and establish the degree of dependence or independence of the variables under consideration, the correlation coefficient statistical tool was adopted for this study.

Table 2 Test of Reliability Using Spearman’s Rank Order Correlation

Responses	Test	Retest	Difference (D)	D ²
Strongly Agree	13	8	5	25
Agree	10	12	2	4
Strongly Disagree	4	8	-4	16
Disagree	5	7	-2	4
Undecided	8	5	3	9
Total				58

Therefore; $r = 1 - \frac{6\sum d^2}{N(N^2 - 1)}$

Where;

r = Spearman’s rank correlation; d = Difference between the observations

n = Number of observations which in this case is 40

$$r = \frac{1 - \frac{6 \times 58}{40(40^2 - 1)}}{1 - \frac{348}{40(1600 - 1)}}$$

$$r = \frac{1 - \frac{348}{40(1599)}}{1 - \frac{348}{63960}}$$

$$r = 1 - 0.005 \quad r = \mathbf{0.995}$$

Data Presentation and Analysis

A total of three hundred and eighty-one (381) copies of questionnaires were distributed to the respondents, out of which three hundred and forty (340) were filled and returned. This represents 89 percent of the total respondents.

According to Igbokwe-Ibeto(2019) some rules of thumb about the return/response rate is that a response rate of 50percent is adequate for analysis and reporting, 60percent is good while 70percent is very good. The high response rate recorded is an indication of the fact that most of

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the respondents displayed positive attitude towards the topic of our research.

Test of Hypotheses

The test of hypotheses for this study was done using the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient. Data utilized for the test were obtained from the responses of respondents to various questions in the questionnaire item that relate to the various hypotheses. A 0.05 level of significance was adopted for the study.

Hypotheses One

H₀: TETFund modalities for funding of staff training and development programmes in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020 are not practicable.

H₁: TETFund modalities for funding of staff training and development programmes in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020 are practicable

Correlations

		TETFund.	Modalities for funding
TETFund	Pearson Correlation	1	.609
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.042
	N	340	340
Modalities for funding	Pearson Correlation	.609	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	.042	
	N	340	340

The result of the correlation coefficient for hypothesis one indicates that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient is 0.609 showing that TETFund has a positive correlation with modalities for funding of staff training and development programmes.

Decision Rule: From the computation above, the probability value at 0.042 is less than 0.05 significant level. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis which states that the TETFund modalities for funding of staff training and development programmes in Nnamdi Azikiwe University,

Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020 are practicable.

Hypotheses Two

H₀: TETFund academic staff training and development programmes has no positive effect on the quality of research output in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020.

H₁: TETFund academic staff training and development programmes has a positive effect on the quality of research output in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020.

Correlations

	TETFund AST&D	Quality of research output

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TETFund AST&D	Pearson Correlation	1	.558
	Sig. (2-tailed)		.045
	N	340	340
	Pearson Correlation	.558	1
Quality of research output	Sig. (2-tailed)	.045	
	N	340	340

The result of the correlation coefficient for hypothesis one indicates that the Pearson Product Moment Correlation Coefficient is 0.558 showing that TETFund academic staff training and development has a positive correlation with quality of research output.

Decision Rule: From the computation above, the probability value at 0.045 is less than 0.05 significant level. Therefore, we reject the null hypothesis and accept the alternative hypothesis which states that TETFund academic staff training and development programmes has a positive effect on the quality of research output in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020.

Summary of Findings

1. TETFund modalities for funding of staff training and development programmes in Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020 are practicable. This finding was obtained from the test of the first hypothesis where the probability value of the correlation (0.042), is less than the level of significant adopted for the study (0.05).
2. TETFund academic staff training and development programmes has a positive effect on the quality of research output in

Nnamdi Azikiwe University, Awka, Anambra State from 2014 to 2020. This finding was obtained from the test of the second hypothesis where the probability value of the correlation (0.045), is less than the level of significant adopted for the study (0.05).

Conclusion

It is appropriate to conclude this academic exercise by reiterating that the human resources of any organization is its most vital asset and thus, the survival and growth of the organization is to a large extent, dependent on it. Staff training and development are some of the best means of getting the best of organizational employees for the success of the organization. Therefore, the development of the human resources in academic institutions is so important as premier organisations in charge of staff training and development. Government intervention through TETFund is not only a step in the right direction, but needs to be strengthened to achieve its intended goals and to this end, we offer the following recommendations.

Recommendations

Based on the findings, the researcher recommended the following;

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1. Bureaucratic bottlenecks in the administration of TETFund should be addressed to make way for speedy processing of applications for staff training and development. This will help to ease many of the challenges of delays and red tapism in the process of application and processing of grant applications.
2. A committee should be set up at the university level to review research output of grant beneficiaries on the completion of their studies. Those that are novel and addresses specific societal challenges should be adopted and channeled to the appropriate government agencies for action to be taken on them.

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